

THE ROLE OF MICRODISCECTOMY IN MODERN NEUROSURGERY: CLINICAL OUTCOMES IN THE TREATMENT OF LUMBAR DISC HERNIATION

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Relevance of the Study. Lumbar disc herniation is one of the most common degenerative-dystrophic diseases worldwide, significantly affecting patients' working capacity and quality of life. In cases where conservative treatment fails to yield results, surgical intervention becomes necessary. In recent years, the introduction of microdiscectomy has marked a new stage in modern neurosurgery.

In this study, microdiscectomy was performed in 60 patients diagnosed with lumbar disc herniation who had not benefited from conservative therapy. Clinical outcomes demonstrated a significant reduction in pain syndromes within the first postoperative days. Moreover, improvement in neurological recovery and restoration of patients' functional activity were observed. The number of recorded complications during follow-up was very low, mostly of mild and temporary nature.

Based on the obtained results, microdiscectomy was found to have several advantages over traditional methods, including minimal invasiveness, shorter operative time, reduced blood loss, shorter rehabilitation period, and faster return of patients to active social life.

Conclusion. The clinical efficacy and safety of microdiscectomy allow it to be recommended as one of the preferred methods for the treatment of lumbar disc herniation in modern neurosurgery. Its widespread implementation plays an important role in reducing the consequences of disease progression and improving patients' quality of life.

References

1. Koebbe C.J., Maroon J.C., Abla A.A., El-Kadi H., Bost J., Cheng B.C. Lumbar microdiscectomy: a historical perspective and current technical considerations // Neurosurgical Focus. – 2002. – Vol. 13, No. 2. – P. E3.

2. Ajiboye R.M., Zoller S.D., D'Oro A., Wang J.C., Hsieh P.C., Skaggs D.L. Surgical Treatment of Recurrent Lumbar Disk Herniation: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis // *Orthopedics*. – 2018. – Vol. 41, No. 4. – P. e457–e469.
3. Kamper S.J., Ostelo R.W., Rubinstein S.M., Nellensteijn J.M., Peul W.C., Arts M.P., van Tulder M.W. Minimally invasive surgery for lumbar disc herniation: a systematic review and meta-analysis // *European Spine Journal*. – 2014. – Vol. 23, No. 5. – P. 1021–1043.
4. Jacobs W.C., van Tulder M., Arts M., Rubinstein S.M., van Middelkoop M., Ostelo R., Verhagen A., Koes B., Peul W.C. Surgery versus conservative management of sciatica due to a lumbar herniated disc: a systematic review // *European Spine Journal*. – 2011. – Vol. 20, No. 4. – P. 513–522.
5. Gulati S., Solberg T.K., Giannadakis C., Nygaard Ø.P., Storheim K., Brox J.I., Hellum C., Brox J.I. Lumbar microdiscectomy for sciatica in adolescents: a multicentre observational registry-based study // *Acta Neurochirurgica (Wien)*. – 2017. – Vol. 159, No. 3. – P. 509–516.
6. Feng Z., Wu W., Chen Y., Liu H., Ding W., Xiao Y., Yang S. Unilateral biportal endoscopic discectomy versus microdiscectomy for lumbar disc herniation: a systematic review and meta-analysis // *Spine Journal*. – 2024. – Vol. 33, No. 6. – P. 2139–2153.
7. Casal-Moro R., Castro-Menéndez M., Hernández-Blanco M., Bravo-Ricoy J.A., Jorge-Barreiro F.J. Long-term Outcome After Microendoscopic Discectomy for Lumbar Disk Herniation: A Prospective Clinical Study With a 5-Year Follow-up // *Neurosurgery*. – 2011. – Vol. 68, No. 6. – P. 1568–1575.